

ONOMATOPOEIC WORDS AND THEIR ROLE IN LANGUAGE ACQUISITION THROUGH CHILDREN'S LITERATURE.

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Abstract

Young children are usually active in producing words between 12 and 18 months of age. They actively acquire words by 'imitating' them from their environment, from their parents or caregivers, from television cartoons, from children's programs on the Internet, and from stories or books that are read or shown to them. Several scientific studies have proven the active use of 'onomatopoeic words' in the speech of young children. In addition, the contribution of onomatopoeia to improving word pronunciation in early language acquisition has also been studied. Therefore, this article explores the work of several linguists on onomatopoeia and their impact on language learning or acquisition through children's literature.

Keywords: young learners, language acquisition, children literature, onomatopoeia, sound symbolism

Introduction

Looking at the history of linguistics, according to English sources, the introduction of onomatopoeic words can be traced back to the 1500s. And in fact, the history of human communication with imitation of sound has been much longer. There is even the assumption that some scholars believe that language is actually created from onomatopoeic words, and that is why these words began to be studied in linguistics under different homogeneous theories. For example, British philologist of the 19th century Friedrich Max Müller (1861) proposes that language originated through onomatopoeia-the imitation of natural sounds like thunder, sneeze, or splash. Later, in the 19th and 20th century, onomatopoeia began to be discussed by Ferdinand de Saussure, founder of structural linguistics. Refer to his sound symbolism theory, onomatopoeia plays the role as *a bridge between sound, meaning, and perception*. Language acquisition is a fundamental concept in the fields of pedagogy, psychology, and linguistics, as it plays a crucial role in children's cognitive and logical development. The process through which individuals acquire language varies depending on cognitive, social, and environmental factors. Since each learner develops language abilities differently, educators and researchers continuously seek effective teaching methodologies and strategies to facilitate successful language learning. Consequently, understanding the mechanisms of language acquisition has become essential for designing pedagogically sound and learner-centered educational practices.

Discussion

Scholars revealed that sound symbolism (a natural connection between sounds (phonemes) and meanings) is very important and helps explaining language acquisition, supports cognitive linguistics. Onomatopoeia is considered to be a universal linguistic phenomenon found in all-natural languages and it is a form of sound symbolism that connects phonetic shape with meaning. As a pragmatic resource it is used to express emotional states, sensory impressions, vivid imagery, and speaker stance. Imai and Kita (2014) suggest that sound symbolism where the phonetic form of a word carries meaning plays a crucial role in both **language acquisition** and **language evolution**. They argue that children are naturally predisposed to associate certain sounds with specific meanings which helps to develop their vocabulary. It shows that onomatopoeic words and other sound-symbolic forms facilitate word learning by providing intuitive links between **sound and meaning** and enhances their ability to acquire language more rapidly. Laing (2017), in her study examines the perceptual advantages of onomatopoeic words during early word

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learning. The research demonstrates that children may have an inherent ability to recognize and process onomatopoeic words due to their **sound-meaning** correspondence. Her research findings suggest that the distinctive auditory features of onomatopoeic words facilitate the learning process, making it easier for children to associate these **words** with their **meanings**. Catherine E. Laing (2019) mentions that onomatopoeic words are more existed in the speech of young children than adults and it is because of the iconic advantage of onomatopoeic words and they are very easy sounds for children to learn. Motamedi et al. (2021) explain that a central issue in early language development is how children learn to map **words** onto **meanings** despite many possible referents and mention that onomatopoeia may support this process because their **sound** structure reflects aspects of **meaning**, enabling children to use sensory cues to form **associations** and they are common in early caregiver speech, and are easier for children to learn than arbitrary words and are used in communicative contexts that enhance learning. Junaid et al. (2023) mention that onomatopoeic words vary significantly across cultures due to differences in language systems and cultural perception and suggest children`s storybooks reflect cultural uniqueness through the use of sound-imitating words adapted to local linguistic patterns. The study shows that similar sounds (e.g., animal noises) are represented differently in different languages. In Uzbek linguistics, onomatopoeia is generally divided into categories of taqlid soʻzlar and tasviriy soʻzlar. Uzbek scholar Qoʻngʻurov, R. (1966) in his monographic study of Uzbek imitative words, classified them into **sound-imitative and image/state-imitative groups**. Another scholar Begmatov, E. (1966) defines tasviriy soʻzlar as lexical units formed through imitation of sounds, movements, and image-like states in the objective world. These researches show that Uzbek onomatopoeia is not limited to acoustic imitation but also includes visual, sensory, and action-based representation. Qurbonova, M. A. (2023) notes that onomatopoeic words are clearly observed in children`s early speech and may function as deictic names. Thus, in Uzbek child language, onomatopoeic forms can serve not only as sound imitation but also as early communicative tools for referring to objects, actions, persons, and states. Many repeated sound-imitative forms such as “miyov-miyov!”, “gʻuv-gʻuv”, “chiriq, chiq-chiriq!”, “vov-vov-vov!”, “gʻoq-gʻoq-gʻoq!”, “gʻa-gʻa-gʻa!” are used in Uzbek children literature and it shows that children are exposed to onomatopoeic forms through stories, poems, and oral-style narrative.

Conclusion

All above research findings and many others demonstrate that onomatopoeic words matter for language acquisition as these types of words are easy to repeat, phonologically simple, emotionally expressive, linked to concrete objects or actions and common in adult-child interaction. Books such as *We're Going on a Bear Hunt* by Michael Rosen & Helen Oxenbury, *Peace at Last* by Jill Murphy, *Moo, Baa, La La La!* by Sandra Boynton, *Mr. Brown Can Moo! Can You?* by Dr. Seuss, *Jā Jā Biri Biri* by Noriko Matsui, *Gatan Goton Gatan Goton* by Yasue Andō richly illustrate this principle. Their rhythmic language, repetitive structure, and vivid imagery encourage early participation in reading and help infants recognize objects through sound. Similar body literature such as traditional poems, songs, and picture books in the Uzbek language for Uzbek children can provide the same developmental benefits. By embracing and promoting such works, educators and parents can support natural language acquisition through the joyful, sound-rich experience of shared reading.

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